

FABRIC Introduction and Tutorial

Paul Ruth
RENCI - UNC Chapel Hill
pruth@renci.org

James Griffioen
University of Kentucky
griff@netlab.uky.edu

Kuangching Wang
Clemson University
kwang@clemson.edu

Abstract—FABRIC project is an NSF Midscale research and education infrastructure that enables experimentation, rapid prototyping, and validation of new network and distributed computing methods and applications that are impossible or impracticable with commonly available research infrastructures.

This tutorial will introduce attendees to the FABRIC testbed, sign them up with an account, and walk them through a hands-on experience with introductory and intermediate example experiments. Example topics will include: 1) Creating and deploying basic experiments, 2) Using wide-area networks, and 3) Using FABRIC’s integrated measurement framework.

Index Terms—networking, testbed, tutorial

I. MOTIVATION

There is a broad range of infrastructure available to the research community, however the awareness of the community of the existence and capabilities of these testbeds remains limited. In fact, for many types of research these testbeds provided the resources and the flexibility to build scalable documented experiments that can then be shared and built upon by others. Importantly many of these platforms, namely FABRIC provide a path to scaling and evolving simple experiments into something that is persistent and can be used by external users, bridging the important valley that lies between a simple prototype and a robust system used by others. This effect where experiments can rapidly grow from simple to complex and become usable and useful systems can have a deep transformative effect on systems and networking research in the immediate future.

FABRIC testbed [Baldin et al.(2019)] was built with many of these ideas in mind - it provides the scale, robustness and programmability to meet these challenges. Even more importantly, FABRIC is designed from the ground up to be a ‘fabric’ that interconnects other experimental and production Cyberinfrastructure (CI) facilities around the world (Figure 1). Thus it achieves a multiplier effect of not only allowing the experimenters to harness its own resources, but to bring to bear the resources and investments in CI in many other disciplines thus vastly increasing the scale and reach of the experiments conducted on it.

II. TUTORIAL ORGANIZATION AND CONTENT

The goal of this tutorial is to introduce participants to the FABRIC platform, its tools and resources and demonstrate how a simple experiment can be transformed into something complex, measurable and shareable. In the first session the

attendees will get a basic introduction to FABRIC and a simple “Hello FABRIC!” experiment. In the second session they will proceed to grow this experiment to spans FABRIC’s geographically distributed resources and employ FABRIC’s measurement framework.

A. Sessions and Length

Session 1 (90 mins):

- **Introduction to FABRIC** (45 mins) - this lecture will describe FABRIC and its capabilities and provide a tour of the portal 2, Jupyter Hub, and documentation.
- **Hello, FABRIC** (45 mins) - in this hands-on component, participants will create FABRIC accounts and run a “Hello FABRIC!” experiment that demonstrates the basic features of the APIs

Session 2 (90 mins):

- **Intermediate Networking Experiment** (45 mins) - in this hands-on component, participants will work under the guidance of tutorial instructors to create a more complex experiment. In this experiment the participants will create a topology across multiple FABRIC locations, deploy a packaged networking experiments, and collect network performance data.
- **FABRIC Measurement Framework** (45 mins) - in this hand-on component, participants will deploy an experiment that utilizes the FABRIC measurement framework to collect low-level performance metrics from their experimental topology.

B. Recommended skill level

Minimum skill set: This tutorial is designed for users who have little or no experience with FABRIC. Basic experience with programming (i.e. python) and an ability to use remote virtual machines is required.

C. Technology and Software Requirements

All hands-on tutorials will use the FABRIC JupyterHub 3. Participants will need a laptop with Internet connectivity, a modern browser, and an SSH client. Specific instructions can be sent in advance for participants to create an account on the research infrastructure and be added to the designated project by the tutorial instructors.

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Fig. 1. FABRIC Infrastructure spanning the U.S., Europe, and Japan

Fig. 2. FABRIC Portal

Fig. 3. FABRIC JupyterHub

III. REFERENCES TO PREVIOUS ITERATIONS OF SIMILAR TUTORIALS

FABRIC team has presented introductory and advanced tutorials covering the GENI, Chameleon, and FABRIC testbeds at various venues over more than a decade. These venues include many of the GENI Engineering Conferences (GECs), Chameleon user meetings, FABRIC KNIT Workshops and other conferences. Recent examples include Internet2 TechEx [Ruth and Ilya(2022)], Massachusetts Open Cloud Alliance Workshop [Ruth(2023c)], SIGCOMM 2023 [Ruth(2023b)], and several FABRIC KNIT workshops [Ruth(2022)], [fab(2023)], [Ruth(2023a)], [Ruth(2024)].

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